

ECONOMIC CONTENT AND NATURE OF INVESTMENTS**Mirazizova Dilafruz Aziz qizi**

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Investments play a very important role in the economy. They are objectively necessary for the development of the economy and sustainable economic self-sufficiency. An active investment process predetermines the economic development of the entire country and helps the population. Economic investments: These are any investments with "normal" profit-making products and products related to real production. "Normal" risk investing refers to purchasing assets in the form of securities for profit.

The economic development of investments is that they directly have a beneficial effect on the economy. They contribute to the improvement of the quality of life of government employees, investor participation, contribution, economic economic policy. Inward investment flows have a greater impact on the development of the economy than outward investment flows.

Investment is profit or capital preservation means putting money into something. An investor is someone who invests their own money to earn income. It can be an individual or a legal entity.

Without investments, it is impossible to ensure the sustainability of the products and services provided, to sell and buy production securities, and to manage funds.

The transfer of market production and full independence to economic entities predetermines the search for new economic development methods. Currently, the production of political-economic theory produces a lot. This is a serious reason for the transition economy and investment process. The main thing here is related to the scientific investment policy and the practical solution will help. In this regard, it is necessary to study investment and investment methods in the science of working with work and support processes [1].

Investments play a major role in the development of macro and micro economy. First of all, expansion of reproduction, implementation of structural changes, increase the profit of the enterprise and, on this basis, create opportunities to positively solve many other problems. The state of investment activity in the country is characterized by the dynamics of the following indicators:

- total volume of investments;

- share of investments in GDP;
- the share of real investments in the total volume of investments;
- technological structure of investments and its change
- general growth of real investments;
- share of foreign investments in investments;
- share of real investments directed to fixed capital;
- share of direct foreign investments in foreign investments, etc [2].

In recent years, the process of structural changes and modernization actively implemented in the economy has further increased investment activity. A significant increase in the volume of investments in the economy from year to year inevitably allows to show its positive results through the growth of the national production volume [1]. As a result of the attention and support given to the development of investment activities on the part of the state, the volume of GDP and the amount of investments will have growth rates. This situation leads to an increase in the weight of investments in GDP.

The importance of investments in the development of the republic's economy is as follows:

1. Introduces modern techniques and technologies to production and develops the production of products intended for export;
2. It makes it possible to start the production of import-substituting goods and to direct foreign investments to the priority sectors of the economy and, ultimately, to ensure the standard of living of the population;
3. Provides jobs for the growing population by developing small business and private entrepreneurship and accelerating agricultural production;
4. Updates and technically re-equips outdated production facilities, material and technical base of enterprises;
5. They help to establish enterprises that process natural resources, etc [3].

In conclusion, investments play a very important role in the economy. They are objectively necessary for the sustainable development of the economy and sustainable economic growth. An active investment process predetermines the economic potential of the entire country and helps to raise the standard of living of the population.

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